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D7.1 Evaluation report on data rates and volumes, and assessment of future needs of LEAPS facilities.

Abbreviations for figures

Spectro	spectroscopy
Im2D	2D imaging
Im3Draw	3D imaging (raw data)
Im3Dproc	3D imaging (processed data)
MX	macromolecular crystallography (single crystal diffraction)
DI	diffraction imaging
PD	powder diffraction
SX	serial crystallography
XPCS	X-ray photon correlation spectroscopy
S(W)AX	small and wide-angle X-ray scattering

Introduction

This report analyses the answers provided by the different LEAPS-INNOV partners to the “data compression and reduction needs” survey sent to all LEAPS-Innov partners on the 15th of July 2022. We will recall each of the thematics that the questions covered and analyse the corresponding answers before establishing general conclusions. The 10 partner facilities who participated to this survey (and their respective abbreviation or short name if relevant) are listed below:

- ALBA-CELLS (Spain)
- DESY (Germany)
- Elettra Sincrotrone (Italy)
- European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF, France)
- European XFEL (Germany)
- Helmholtz Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie (HZB, Germany)
- Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR, Germany)
- MAX IV Laboratory (MAXIV, Sweden)
- NSRC SOLARIS (Poland)
- Synchrotron SOLEIL (France)

For each facility, the answers were provided either by the LEAPS-Innov WP7 local coordinator, or by a contact scientist or software developer.

1) Techniques and compression needs

1.1 Annual data volume:

Facility	2020	2025
Elettra	0.3	1.1
MAX IV	1.0	3.0
SOLEIL	0.8	5.0
SOLARIS	0.16	10.0
ALBA	0.07	11.5
DESY	2	15.0
EuXFEL	12	40.0
ESRF	10	60.0
HZB	0.2	NaN
HZDR	NaN	NaN

fig 1: (left) data volume (PB) produced in 2020 and foreseen in 2025 for each of the 10 partner facilities (NaN: data not available). (right) graphical representation highlighting the percentage of increase over the 5 years considered.

The trend is that between 2020 and 2025, facilities expect a two to six-fold increase in the volume of data produced. Some like ALBA and SOLARIS will undergo a much more pronounced increase due to the forthcoming installation of several data-intensive instruments (e.g cryoEM, serial crystallography and μ CT in the case of ALBA) in the upcoming years.

1.2 Data throughput

Highest sustained (not buffered) raw throughput for data acquisition on one instrument

fig2: Highest sustained raw data throughput for data acquisition in the 10 partner facilities (note that HZDR reported an maximum rate of 100 GB/s, but this was removed as it corresponds to simulation rather than experimental data)

The range of raw data throughput (per instrument) follows the evolution of detectors - the cap at 16 GBytes/s (128 Gb/s) corresponds to a 4 MPixel detector operating at 2 kHz. Note that this throughput can imply dedicated network links (multiple fibre optic cables, facility ethernet links usually operate at 25 or 100 Gb/s). These rates imply on-the-fly data compression or reduction, as high-performance filesystems (e.g. GPFS) can only deliver up to a few Gbyte/s. A continued increase of the overall throughput and framerate is expected in the near future.

2) Data compression and reduction approaches

2.1 Compression ratio achieved vs needed

fig 3: Technique-wise compression ratio (raw volume/archived volume) achieved and needed. The bars indicate the most frequent answer (the largest compression ratio in case of equal frequencies).

*fig 4: Technique-wise compression ratio (raw volume/archived volume) needed.
(overall=including compression, reduction and triage of data)*

The y-axis indicates the number of responses while the compression ratio is colour-coded.

Fig.3 and 4 show that the techniques for which a high compression (or reduction) ratio is needed (x100) are serial crystallography, small and wide-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS/WAXS) and X-ray photon correlation spectroscopy. This can be understood as reflecting the sparse nature of the corresponding raw images produced (XPCS, serial Xtallography) by these techniques, which in theory would favour background removal and triage in addition to pure compression. For SAXS/WAXS and powder diffraction, the ratio corresponds to a 2D->1D data reduction via azimuthal integration. Tomographic techniques (3D imaging) on the other hand are much less amenable to noise-reduction so that a maximum compression ratio of 10X can be expected.

2.2 Other techniques mentioned by some of the partners:

ALBA	cryo/material EM
Elettra	XRF, Ptychography, CDI, and FEL based techniques (FERMI)
EuXFEL	Single particle imaging (SPI) X-ray cross-correlation analysis (XCCA) Scanning transmission X-ray microscopy (STXM)
HZB	SEM / FIB tomography
HZDR	Digital twins and simulation
MAX IV	Event-based data

2.3 Regarding compression, what is really important? (multiple answers possible)

fig 5: Global (top, blue barplot) and technique-wise (bottom, multicolor bar plots) distributions of factors considered important for compression.

From these answers, one of the factors that contributors considered of prime importance for compression is that it must be **transparent for users**. This is a challenge as the implementation of new, more efficient compression techniques (lossy or not) requires that *all* facility users be able to perform decompression without effort, and this implies a high level of standardisation for the compression codecs (e.g. across multiple frameworks and languages like python, matlab etc..).

Compression and decompression speed are also considered important, with a slight preference for compression speed, which can be explained by the need of making compression one of the steps of high-throughput (up to 16 GB/s) data acquisition pipelines. The compression ratio is particularly important for imaging techniques.

2.4 Regarding compression, what compression/reduction methods are needed?(multiple answers possible)

fig 6: Technique-wise compression approaches

Generic compression algorithms (e.g. based on gzip, or other codecs which can be transparently used across many software and platforms) are frequently mentioned for all techniques. Lossy compression appears primarily in imaging techniques (where JPEG codecs are already used in the community to ease the data transfer) while diffraction techniques favour data reduction (e.g. azimuthal integration from 2D to 1D for SAXS/WAXS and powder diffraction). Note that data selection (triage) is less often chosen, except in crystallography techniques and somewhat in SAXS/WAXS.

Alternatively, the reader might find useful to visualise the answers by technique using a word cloud representation (fig. 7, where the size of each word is representative of the number of answers):

fig 7: Word cloud representation of the answers provided regarding the compression/reduction methods needed in each category of technique.

3) Conclusion

We observe a general increase in data volumes and rates already started for large facilities but also coming to smaller ones along with more high-volume techniques (imaging, CryoEM, etc) and faster detectors. The need for compression is coming first from facilities, who need to lower both the short-term data storage (disk arrays during data collection), as well as the longer-term storage as all experimental data needs to be kept for a long period as a consequence of open data policies which imply a retention of at least 5-10 years. The users are also in need of compression, in order to be able to transfer the data to their home institution, and to store the data until it is fully exploited.

Regarding the algorithms, beyond the need for the most efficient compression (speed and compression ratio), a key issue is the transparent nature for the end users, who should not need to deploy specific libraries in their software of choice in order to be able to open compressed files. This is a tough requirement given the diversity of software which can open experimental data files, and will require to focus on a very high level of standardisation, more than the raw compression performance.

Looking more specifically at techniques which produce high levels of raw data, SAXS/WAXS and powder diffraction are the most well-established, and have data reduction pipelines which are standardised, so that keeping the raw original data may not be necessary. Serial Crystallography is a more recently established technique (with modern synchrotron sources and XFELs), and the data reduction pipelines are still evolving. Last but not least, 3D imaging (tomography) techniques are the most demanding due to the inability to reduce either raw or processed data: it is clearly for this family of techniques that an effort should be made to completely evaluate lossy compression approaches, both in terms of performance and acceptability from the scientific community.

4) Annex

4.1 Links to software repositories

Facility	Links to software repositories
DESY	https://stash.desy.de/
ESRF	https://github.com/silx-kit/hdf5plugin https://github.com/silx-kit/pyFAI https://github.com/silx-kit/dynamix
EuXFEL	https://github.com/European-XFEL/EXtra-data https://github.com/European-XFEL/EXtra-geom https://github.com/European-XFEL/geoAssembler https://git.xfel.eu/gitlab/dataAnalysis/data-reduction https://git.xfel.eu/gitlab/esobolev/batch-azimuthal-int https://git.xfel.eu/gitlab/dataAnalysis/validate-recent-runs https://git.xfel.eu/gitlab/dataAnalysis/crystfel_spb_workflow/tree/master
MAX IV	https://gitlab.com/MAXIV-SCISW https://github.com/MaxIV-KitsControls https://github.com/maxiv-science https://gitlab.maxiv.lu.se
(other)	Software repository for the BLOSC compression library project: https://github.com/Blosc

4.2 Existing documents regarding compression techniques

Facility	Documents
DESY	Some tests of accelerator cards for data compression: http://www.desy.de/~yuelong/hc.pdf
ESRF	ESRF Information Technology Data Strategy 2022 - 2026 https://zenodo.org/record/5155787#.Yjip6JqZPUl
Elettra	Lossy compression for CT data: https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1361-6501/aaa0fa

	triage: https://patents.google.com/patent/US20140328546A1/
EuXFEL	Egor Sobolev "Data reduction", European XFEL Science Days 2020 (presentation, 30.11.2020, https://www.xfel.eu/sites/sites_custom/site_xfel/content/e35152/e35161/e127088/e129744/e129991/xfel_file130531/08_Sobolev_eng.pdf)
HZDR	"On the Scalability of Data Reduction Techniques in Current and Upcoming HPC Systems from an Application Perspective" https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-67630-2_2
MAX IV	DataStaMP: https://www.maxiv.lu.se/accelerators-beamlines/technology/kits-projects/datastamp
PSI	J. Synchrotron Rad. (2020). 27, 1326-1338, "Impact of lossy compression of X-ray projections onto reconstructed tomographic slices" https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600577520007353

